

6.1

STAR4BBS stakeholder map

Unitelma Sapienza
università degli studi di Roma

Funded by
the European Union

www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

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6.1

STA4BBS stakeholder map

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Serena Fabbrini

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Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
SERENA FABBRINI	APRE

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
LUANA LADU	TUB
CHIARA POCATERRA	APRE

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Partners short names

TUB	(Technische Universität Berlin)
UNITELMA	(Università degli studi Unitelma di Roma)
UNI	(Ente Italiano di Normazione)
AUA	(Geoniko Panepistimion Athinon)
USC	(Universidad de Santiago de Compostela)
APRE	(Agenzia per la promozione della Ricerca Europea)
NOVA	(Nova - Institut für politische und Ökologische Innovation GMBH)
BAM	(Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und Prüfung)
RSB	(Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials Association)
ISEAL	(ISEAL Alliance)

Abbreviations

EU	European Union
SCS	Sustainability Certification Schemes
B2B	Business to business
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
GA	Grant Agreement
M	Month
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
DB	Database
PP	Privacy policy
WP	Work package
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations

Executive summary

The purpose of this document is to support the project team of STAR4BBS in the organization of activities with a strong participative component. The intention is to allow partners to use the mutual learning events as opportunities for co-creation of new knowledge, considering the planning of these engagement opportunities in their full potential.

STAR4BBS Consortium will engage relevant stakeholders from the very beginning of the project to ensure that information, needs, knowledge and experience of relevant stakeholders are collected throughout the entire duration of the project.

This document will define different steps that project partners shall take into account before and when interacting with the different stakeholders in the mutual learning events (e.g. co-creation workshops).

1 STAR4BBS methodological approach

A *stakeholder* is a person, or an organization, or a group of people that has a concrete interest in and impacted by the outcomes/results of any actions. Common examples of stakeholders: policymakers and governments, customers, end users, suppliers, communities. For STAR4BBS purpose and aims, considered stakeholders should be (among others, see Chapter 1.3):

- Certification scheme owners
- Label owners
- Value chains actors
- EU Policymakers
- Intergovernmental organizations (e.g. FAO)
- Researchers and academic communities
- Industry actors
- Civil society and end-consumer organizations
- NGOs

Stakeholder engagement is one of the dimensions considered in the European Commission's RRI framework. Through participation and involvement, it contributes to improve mutual understanding between science and society, by implementing principles of inclusion, adaptability, reactivity and desirability. It can be defined as a concrete measure targeted to support and improve the dialogue between science and society. Activities, constructive dialogue and exchange of ideas are at the core of the stakeholder engagement to better understand and integrate different perspectives, needs and interests at stake in a given solution. Stakeholder engagement is a practice that involves a two-way interaction between researchers and stakeholders and which can trespass onto co-creation.

Stakeholder mapping is part of the stakeholder analysis. It is an exercise where relevant stakeholders can be identified and then categorized to help with the implementation of the engagement strategy.

This process consists of listing all relevant stakeholder on a map in order to help to see all people who can influence the project and it also shows how they are interlinked. In the stakeholder mapping the single stakeholders are grouped.

During the lifetime of the project, partners will engage different stakeholders' groups according to their activities. In the first months of the project, APRE established the workflow to create the first core of the STAR4BBS database (DB).

1.1 Creation of the database

STAR4BBS partners have dedicated a specific effort to the creation of the stakeholders' DB through the leveraging of existing platforms networks, contacts, initiatives, similar projects and the mapping of the stakeholders.

As defined during the proposal phase of STAR4BBS, the starting point for the construction of the DB was the Community build during the implementation of STAR-

ProBio¹, a Horizon 2020 funded project coordinated by a Beneficiary of STAR4BBS (UNITELMA) which involved some other STAR4BBS partners (e.g. TUB, AUA, USC).

UNITELMA, before sharing the invitation to join STAR4BBS Community, updated STAR-ProBio DB, by checking its subscribers according to the criteria considered for the implementation of STAR4BBS' activities. Thus, STAR-ProBio database was correctly updated before the sharing of the invitation to join STAR4BBS Community, according to Milestone 1 (STAR-ProBio database updated, due to the end of February 2023).

Taking into account the EU General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR) it was not possible to transfer all the contact details collected during the implementation of previously EU funded projects where the different partners are involved. In order to build up STAR4BBS DB, APRE created a subscription form (see Annex 3.1). This form has been shared among all the network already developed in previous EU projects in which partners were involved and will also draw on the broad networks and knowledge of project partners and associated partners. APRE studied a dedicated Privacy Policy (PP) (Annex 3.2) in order to provide to each subscriber a clear Regulation about the use and purpose of the data collected². This PP will be available on the website³.

The DB has been structured taking into account the information needed in the different phases and activities of the project:

- Contact details (name, email, organization, website);
- Category
- Localization (country) in order to have the possibility to involve the stakeholders in the activities of the Macro-regions

The DB will be continuously updated and widened via networking initiatives, dissemination activities and searching online public records. All the information collected is stored in the APRE server and will be kept confidential taking into account the GDPR rules.

At the beginning of November 2022, the DB started to collect contact information.

As the categorization of the stakeholder will take into account outputs and results of WPs 1-5, in this first phase of the stakeholders' mapping it was decided to simply ask to the participants to self-categorize him/herself according to the prioritization category of interest:

1. Certification scheme owners;
2. Academia / Research organization;
3. Industry;
4. Policymaker / Public institution
5. Civil society;
6. NGO;
7. Association (e.g. consumers, employers' organization)

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727740/it>

² As defined at the end of the STAR4BBS subscription form, data is collected following EU GDPR [Article 6.1.a and 6.1.f].

³ <https://star4bbs.eu/privacy-policy/>

8. Other (to be specified)

Figure 1 STAR4BBS Subscription form, category (143 participants, January 2023)

Depending on the results obtained in previous WPs, topics of the workshops will be decided and then stakeholders will be selected from the DB. From this second level of targeting (e.g. STAR4BBS will invite policymakers to participate to a workshop focusing on regulations and policies), invitation to participate to co-creation activities will be sent.

While STAR4BBS will be implemented, new stakeholders will be reached (thanks to the promotion of STAR4BBS activities) to collect data and increase the DB.

1.2 Online subscription form

APRE has created an online subscription form that has been linked to the project website⁴. The form includes personal information (Name, Surname and e-mail address) that will be handled taking into account the privacy principles and good practices in meeting data protection requirements: each user has to agree on the use of the personal data and can access the information sheet of the project⁵. Additionally, they can be deleted from the database at any time upon request. Aim of the form is also to categorize the stakeholder to enable the further retrieval and cluster based on the type and sector.

In order to populate the DB, APRE has asked for its promotion to STAR4BBS partners via their contacts and networks/channels and, also, to the former EU funded projects coordinators of the consortium to contact the stakeholders of their databases or using their networks/channels. In order to do that, APRE shared a standard communication presenting the project (Annex 4.3).

The registration form is also promoted via communication tools (e.g. project website, social media) with a specific QR Code, that has been generated in order to reach the

⁴ <https://star4bbs.eu/join-our-community/>

⁵ For more information, please refer to STAR4BBS, D8.3 “Ethical Issues Report”, Annex 2 (page 14).

link easily in any circumstances. All project's partners have a dedicated effort to share this information among their networks, thus for the population of the DB.

Figure 2 QR Code for STAR4BBS DB Subscription form

1.3 Stakeholder mapping: identified categories

Figure 3 Identification of potential relevant stakeholders, internal exercise on Miro

An internal consultation between APRE, TUB, NOVA, ISEAL and UNITELMA (all partners are involved in Task 6.1), brought to the identification of **seven categories of relevant stakeholders** who will be involved during the implementation of each task:

1. Standards setting, labelling and certification organisations (even certification bodies);
2. Academia, research institutions and researchers;
3. Value chains actors (feedstocks producers, processors and industry bodies);
4. EU Policymakers;
5. Intergovernmental organizations (e.g. FAO);
6. Civil society organizations and end-consumers;
7. EU funded projects on the same topic

Another considered target are the “Financial institutions” but according to STAR4BBS’ aims and goals they will be engaged only if the Consortium will encounter topics and issues regarding a financial aspect.

While projects’ activities will be implemented, other relevant targets could be appointed.

2 Stakeholder engagement in STAR4BBS

2.1 What is stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement is a practice that involves a two-way interaction between researchers and stakeholders. As such, stakeholder engagement contributes to improving communication and understanding of a problem, while getting insight from specific stakeholders. The engagement of stakeholders brings the participant of an event to a circular process that grows out mutual exchanges, insights, feedback and frequency of interactions.

Stakeholder engagement is required when certain problems must be analysed and solved because:

1. there is a strong normative component behind it;
2. the solution will involve a large number of people, whose perspectives must be taken into account;
3. single-people knowledge and expertise alone are not enough to catch the solution;
4. it is a *wicked problem*: wicked problems are characterized by high levels of complexity, ambiguity, and low levels of predictability on their evolution⁶.

First of all, in order to setup the stakeholder engagement activity, it's important to identify stakeholders' interests and motivations for participating in such activity. Then, choose the best activity to do, such as:

- **Mobilisation and Mutual Learning events** (MML): are one means of ensuring the engagement of all relevant groups and aim to tackle research and innovation related challenges by creating partnerships with a variety of perspectives, knowledge and experience⁷. The quality and impact of the MML workshop is dependent on a relevant and clear outcome, output, and topic. Moreover, the ability to attract participants who can actually contribute and who have an action potential is crucial.
- **World café**: a flexible and simple format for hosting large group dialogues. Participants explore the same question in multiple, parallel conversations, and then people rotate to different tables (or breakout rooms) to exchange ideas. Towards the end, the group often takes time to make common meaning of the patterns they have discussed⁸. A simple structure of a World café could be
 - a. *Preparation of the room, or access to the virtual room*: a friendly environment with tables, flipcharts and sticky notes (for the virtual version, Miro can be used);
 - b. *Welcome and introduction by the facilitator*;

⁶ The term wicked problem was coined in the mid-1960s by design theorist Horst Rittel to indicate a problem that is "unique, ambiguous and [that] has no definite solution". Rittel argues that science cannot solve ambiguous and evolving problems, but a more creative approach is needed and since every wicked problem is unique, its "solution" process must also be unique.

⁷ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_HCO-15-2014 (last accessed, 23/01/2023)

⁸ <https://theworldcafe.com/> (last accessed, 23/01/2023)

- c. *First round of conversation, small groups*: for the virtual version, in separate breakout rooms. Each group focuses on a single question/topic (suggested time: 20 minutes);
 - d. *Second round of conversation, plenary group*: after the small conversation, plenary exchange will be organised, to share insights or other results from small groups with the rest of the participants.
- **Open space**: designed to allow a group to self-organize in the exploration of a relevant topic of concern. The group discusses the shared question in breakout sessions with a self-organized agenda. Topics come to the fore suggested by participants who have enough expertise and responsibility to explore them⁹.
 - **Design thinking**: known also as “five-step approach”, design thinking helps a group of people from a shared understanding of a problem to a way to prototype and test solutions. The five known steps are (1) Empathize, (2) Define, (3) Ideate, (4) Prototype, (5) Test¹⁰.
 - **Brainstorming**: collecting several ideas from a group of participants.
 - **Co-creation and co-design**: requires the involvement of participant in teams (even in plenary sessions), it’s a process that is enhanced through designed activities that aims at unleashing individual creativity in a meaning sharing, sense-making, decision-making collective experience¹¹.

All the above approaches could be conducted both online and onsite. APRE, as leader of Task 6.2, can bring to STAR4BBS’ activities several online useful tools that can be used in such occasions:

- **Miro**: a collaborative whiteboard platform that enables participants to work together, from brainstorming with digital sticky notes to planning and managing agile workflows;
- **Slido**: a question and answers and polling platform for online, onsite or hybrid events;
- **Mentimeter**: an online tool to share polls and reach feedback in an interactive way.

⁹ <https://openspaceworld.org/wp2/explore/> (last accessed, 23/01/2023)

¹⁰ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/design-thinking> (last accessed, 23/01/2023)

¹¹ <https://www.interaction-design.org/literature/topics/co-creation#:~:text=Co%2Dcreation%20is%20the%20practice,product%20or%20service%20should%20include> (last accessed, 23/01/2023)

2.2 How to organize an event to engage stakeholders

For both online and onsite events, it's important to invite experts for keynote speeches. They can bring their expertise to the discussion as a showcase of success cases and stories, role models, the point of view of a High-Level Institution. In the preparation for an engagement event, it is important to define the intended output and outcome, otherwise it is challenging to have a focused and meaningful dialogue that actually sets change in motion. The **output** refers to the results which are achieved immediately after implementing an activity. The **outcome** refers to longer-term results, for instance follow-up activities undertaken by specific participants.

The **Agenda** should include:

1. the *abstract* of the event and the expected results (e.g. output and outcomes);
2. the *subscription form*: this is very important and must include at least these field:
 - a. Name
 - b. Surname
 - c. Email
 - d. Organization
 - e. Country
3. The actual agenda to the day with the speakers and topic

Other fields be added according to the aim of the event.

The registration form should include the field regarding the *Consent from*, like:

- I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for [Registration of the participation in NAME OF EVENT/DATE]
- STAR4BBS is committed to ensuring the security and protection of the personal information that we process, and to provide a compliant and consistent approach to data protection. You can find detailed information about the content and scope of the processing of your data in our Privacy Policy: <https://star4bbs.eu/privacy-policy/>
 - I understand that my personal data will be held and processed in confidence and in accordance with the principles laid out by GDPR [article 6.1.a and 6.1.f]
- Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that you do not consent to the relevant subject:
 - I agree to appear in pictures/videos that may be taken during the activity as evidence of the activity itself and as possible promotional material for the STAR4BBS project. I understand that these pictures will not be provided to any organisations for commercial purposes. However, they may be processed by third parties as a consequence of their dissemination at international level through the project's social media and website. I understand that the consortium has no control on the images after dissemination.
 - I allow STAR4BBS to retain my contact details for future activities of the project, to be inserted in STAR4BBS Database.
- I agree to be added to STAR4BBS mailing list, in order to receive the Newsletter and other information about project's activities.

- I agree
- I do not agree

After the event, it is useful to gather minutes of the event in a *Report* (see annex 3.4). The report of the activity should be submitted on the Project repository [WP6 > T6.2 > *select the folder of the event*] by 30 days of the implementation of the activity.

2.3 STAR4BBS tasks and stakeholders engagement

The following table shows, for each task of the project, the stakeholders that will be involved in workshops. Topics of each activity will be decided according to the results obtained by each task leader (and partners involved) and starting from the expected outcome of the activity itself. The proper format of each activity will be defined according to the objectives and the needs of the partners. It's advisable to start thinking about the activity at least a month before its implementation. This time will allow the Organizer and the facilitators to formulate a clear topic, define the right methodology and activities, and gather participants according to the expected outcomes.

Numbers of each category of stakeholders refer to the list in Chapter 1.3.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8 (others)
Task 1.1				x				
Task 1.2	x	x						
Task 1.3	x	x						
Task 1.4								
Task 1.5	x	x			x	x	x	
Task 2.1			x					
Task 2.2	x		x					
Task 2.3			x				x	
Task 3.1	x	x		x	x		x	
Task 3.2	x	x		x	x		x	
Task 3.3	x	x		x	x		x	
Task 4.2	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Task 4.3	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Task 5.1		x	x				x	
Task 5.2	x	x	x	x	x		x	
Task 5.3	x	x	x	x	x		x	
Task 5.4							x	
Task 5.5		x	x				x	
Task 5.6	x		x					
Task 6.2	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Task 6.3	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Task 7.3							x	
Task 7.4	x	x	x	x	x		x	

Table 2 Stakeholders involved per each task

3 Conclusions

This document aims at transferring methodological guidelines to STA4BBS partners for the implementation of activities with a stakeholders' engagement component. Nevertheless, it could be the starting point for everyone interested in the implementation of activities which involve different group of stakeholders.

This document will be directly tested by the consortium in the upcoming events, with a view to make the most out of the in-the-field feedback and operational experience, aiming at improving the way to provide future support to participative research and stakeholder engagement events.

4 Annexes

4.1 STAR4BBS DB subscription form

STAR4BBS Database Subscription | Join our community!

The overall aim of the STAR4BBS, a three-year EU funded project, is to **maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and B2B labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy**. At the core of the STAR4BBS project is the development of indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. This information will create the foundations to support achieving the much-needed harmonization between schemes and transparency in global and EU trade flows.

Through the developed new monitoring system, existing SCS and labels will be analyzed, and the results, as well as additional research on certified and uncertified trade flows and on the impacts of costs and benefits of certification schemes and labels, will substantially increase understanding of the potential of these schemes to contribute to policy and industry sustainability goals and will build awareness of the differences between the schemes. The project will involve important stakeholders (including scheme owners, policy makers, and industry actors) in validation of the concept and the design of the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis to ensure that the project achieves its ultimate goal. An increased uptake of the most effective SCS and labels by the bio-based industry will support the development of circular, climate-neutral, sustainable biobased systems that will mitigate climate change, increase resource efficiency, preserve and restore ecosystems, biodiversity, natural resources, and the quality of air, water and soil.

This consent form is designed to collect expressions of interest to be part of STAR4BBS Stakeholders Database, projects financed by the European Commission. All the data collected shall not be used outside STAR4BBS activities and will be processed following the EU GDPR [article 6.1.a and 6.1.f] and STAR4BBS Privacy Policy [go to <https://star4bbs.eu/>]

By subscribing this form, you will receive:

- Invitation to project-related events, especially the co-creation workshops planned for 2023
- News of relevant activities and initiatives implemented in the context of bioeconomy-related EU projects in which STAR4BBS consortium is involved
- Project Newsletters (released every 5 months)

For further information, please contact Dr. Luana Ladu (TUB), project coordinator:

luana.ladu@tu-berlin.de

CORDIS page of STAR4BBS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060588>

1. Name *

2. Surname *

3. Organization *

4. Organization website *

5. Country *

6. e-mail *

7. Category *

- Certification schemes owners
- Academia / Research organization
- Industry
- Policymaker / Public institution
- Civil society
- NGO
- Association (e.g. consumers, employers' organization)
- Altro

8. The information you will send will be stored and processed through email only for the purpose of receiving information about the activities and events of the project. The data you will submit will be used by STAR4BBS. STAR4BBS will treat your personal information with all the confidentiality and security in accordance with the established data protection regulations. You may withdraw your consent to use the data at any time, by sending an email to: star4bbs@apre.it *

- I agree

Questo contenuto non è stato creato né approvato da Microsoft. I dati che invii verranno recapitati al

4.2 STAR4BBS Privacy Policy

PRIVACY NOTICE PURSUANT TO ARTICLE 13 OF REGULATION (EU) 2016/679

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The information is given in compliance with article 13 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation or GDPR) to individuals interested in receiving news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters relating to the activities conducted by STAR4BBS, managed by APRE (mail to star4bbs@apre.it).

Definitions

“Personal data” (article 4, paragraph 1 of the GDPR) means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

“Processing” (article 4, paragraph 2 of the GDPR) means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

Data Controller

For the purposes of the GDPR (article 24) the Data Controller is:

APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea,
via Cavour 71 – 00184 Rome – Italy
e-mail segreteria@apre.it
Tel +39 6 48939993

Type of data processed

As part of our activities, APRE collect and use personal data provided by you, the data subject, e.g. name, surname, email, organization to the extent that is needed and helpful to attain the purposes set out below.

Purpose of processing and profiling

We may collect and use personal data for the following purposes:

- Applications, registrations, access and administrative management of Users;

- Communication and promotion of the activities of the project e.g. news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters via e-mail; as well as analysis and research;

Enabling the Service Provider to address and handle claims or litigations.

Personal data may be collected also for profiling purposes (off by default). Specifically, we may ask you to give information about your areas of interest so that you receive communications that are targeted to your preferences.

You can change your preferences at any time.

Legal basis for processing personal data

For the purposes set out above, the legal basis of processing is the consent you, the data subject, give to the processing of your personal data, [article 6.1.a) of the GDPR].

and for the legitimate interest of the Service Provider (i.e. security monitoring) [article 6.1.f) of the GDPR]

Data Subject Rights

In relation to your personal data you can exercise your rights as data subject under the GDPR, namely:

- Right of access [article 15 of the GDPR];
- Right to rectification [article 16 of the GDPR];
- Right to erasure ("right to be forgotten") [article 17 of the GDPR];
- Right to restriction of processing [article 18 of the GDPR];
- Right to data portability [article 20 of the GDPR];
- Right to object [article 21 of the GDPR].

You have the right to withdraw your consent at any time.

The rights set out above can be exercised in writing by sending an email to star4bbs@apre.it.

You as data subject have also the right to lodge a complaint with the Italian Data Protection Authority (*Garante per la protezione dei dati personali*).

For further information about data subjects rights visit our website www.star4bbs.eu.

Data retention

Your personal data will be kept until the date of withdrawal of consent. Any longer storage periods remain unaffected, in the event that they are required due to legal, accounting and/or fiscal obligations.

After the storage period, as described above, the data you have provided will be erased.

Consent to data processing

You are free to give or withhold your consent to processing of your personal data for the purposes above. We need your freely given consent to send you news, information, invitations to events and workshops, publications, announcements and newsletters regarding our activities. Should you deny your consent, we will be unable to send you said communications.

Disclosure of data outside of the APRE

We may disclose your personal data outside of our Association for specific reasons. In particular, your personal data may be made available to entities providing IT system management on behalf of our Association, competent authorities and/or public bodies, European Commission, and supervisory authorities to comply with statutory requirements. Where appropriate, we shall formally appoint said third parties Data Processors pursuant to article 28 of the GDPR.

How data is processed

Your data will be processed our controller's employees and other authorized individuals. Said employees, and other authorized individuals may consult, use, process, compare the data as well as carry out any other appropriate action, including using automated means, always in compliance with statutory requirements that ensure, inter alia, protection of the confidentiality and security of the personal data, as well as data accuracy, update and appropriateness to the purposes for which the data is collected and used, as stated above.

Transfer of data outside of the EU

Your Data will not be transferred outside the European Union.

Changes and updates

APRE may make changes and/or additions to this privacy notice including as a result of regulatory changes.

General Information about cookies

Definition of "cookies". Cookies are short fragments of text (letters and/or numbers) that allow the web server to store in regard to the client (the browser, e.g. Internet Explorer, Chrome, Firefox, Opera, etc.) information to be reused during visits to the site (session cookies) or later, even after days (persistent cookies). Cookies are stored, according to user preferences, by the single browser on the specific device used (computer, tablet, etc.).

Based on the characteristics and use of cookies, various types of cookies can be distinguished:

Technical cookies strictly necessary. These cookies are essential for the proper functioning of a website that are used to manage various services related to websites (for example, logins or access to the reserved functions in the sites). The duration of cookies is strictly limited to the work session Deactivation of strictly necessary cookies may compromise the user experience and navigation of the website.

Purposes of the processing and purposes of technical session cookies. The cookies used on the Site are for the sole purpose of performing computer authentication or the monitoring of sessions and the storage of specific technical information concerning users accessing the servers of the Data Controller that manages the Site. In this view, some activities on the Website cannot be performed without the use of cookies, which in such cases are therefore technically necessary.

CONSENT REQUEST PURSUANT TO ARTICLE 6 OF THE GDPR

By clicking on the "Sign up" button in the subscription form you give your consent to our processing of your personal data in accordance with the purposes described above.

December 2022

4.3 Standard communication presenting the project

Dear NAME&SURNAME,

You might be interested in this new Horizon Europe funded project which aims at developing indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems.

The overall aim of STAR4BBS is to maximize the potential of Sustainability Certification Schemes (SCS) and labels to support a successful transition to sustainable bio-based economy. At the core of the STAR4BBS project is the development of indicators and a new monitoring system for assessing the effectiveness and robustness of existing international and EU SCS, B2B labels, and related traceability systems applicable to biological feedstock and bio-based materials and products. This information will create the foundations to support achieving the much-needed harmonization between schemes and transparency in global and EU trade flows.

Through the developed new monitoring system, existing SCS and labels will be analyzed, and the results, as well as additional research on certified and uncertified trade flows and on the impacts and costs and benefits of certification and labels, will substantially increase understanding of the potential of these schemes to contribute to policy and industry sustainability goals and will build awareness of the differences between the schemes.

The project will involve important stakeholders (including scheme owners, policy makers, and industry) in the design of research and the monitoring system and in the development of practical recommendations emerging from the research and analysis in order to ensure that the project achieves its ultimate goal. In particular, an increased uptake of the most effective SCS and labels by the bio-based industry will support the development of circular, climate-neutral, sustainable biobased systems that will mitigate climate change, increase resource efficiency, preserve and restore ecosystems, biodiversity, natural resources, and the quality of air, water and soil.

For more information about STAR4BBS and to subscribe to our community, please visit: www.star4bbs.eu

Hope to hear your voice soon,

STAR4BBS Team

4.4 Report of the event

STAR4BBS representative (name and organization)	
Event venue (or online platform)	
Date	
WP	
Task	

Title	
Total number of participants, out of which	
Standards setting, labelling and certification organisations (even certification bodies)	
Academia/research institutions/researchers	
Value chains actors (feedstocks producers, processors and industry bodies)	
EU Policymakers	
Intergovernmental organizations	
Civil society organizations and end - consumers	
EU funded projects	
Other (specify)	

Rationale or Purpose of your Event	
Main challenges addressed	
Speakers invited	
Main outcomes	
<p>Summarise the agenda Describe and motivate the focus Key points from the event: describe the main points/conclusions from the event Key points from the main challenge(s) and the context addressed: describe the main points/conclusions from each challenge(s) Outcomes per challenge: new collaborations, follow-up of activities, recommendations Evaluation report: describe and analyse any feedback Selected publishable photos</p>	

List of participants		
Name	Surname	Organization

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“ Sustainable bio-based systems via effective certification & labelling ”

Consortium:

Unitelma Sapienza
università degli Studi di Roma

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www.star4bbs.eu
info@star4bbs.eu

@STAR4BBS

